

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN CAPSULE DOSAGE FORM

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 10/10/2020
Available online
31/01/2021

Keywords

Venlafaxine Hydrochloride,
RP-HPLC,
Capsule Dosage Form.

ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, specific and accurate RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the estimation of venlafaxine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage form. The method involved an isocratic elution of venlafaxine hydrochloride in ODS C18 column using mobile phase consists of methanol : ortho-phosphoric acid (90:10 v/v). The wavelength of detection was 225 nm. The method showed good linearity in the range of 7.5-37.5 µg/mL with correlation coefficient of 0.9981. The retention time was 2.41 min. The method was statistically validated for accuracy, precision, linearity, ruggedness, robustness, solution stability, selectivity and sensitivity. The results obtained in the study were within the limits of ICH guidelines. The results showed that this method can be used for rapid determination of venlafaxine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical capsule dosage form with precision, accuracy and specificity. The proposed method can be used for routine quality control samples in industry in for the estimation of venlafaxine hydrochloride in bulk and in finished dosage form.

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Please cite this article in press as **T Hemant Kumar et al.** RP-HPLC Method for the Estimation of Venlafaxine Hydrochloride in Capsule Dosage Form . *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2021;11(01).

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INTRODUCTION

Venlafaxine hydrochloride chemically is (Figure 1), (1-[2-dimethylamino)-1-(4-methoxy phenyl) ethyl] cyclohexanol hydrochloride is a third generation antidepressant[1]. It inhibits the reuptake of serotonin, norepinephrine and to a lesser extent dopamine. It lacks monoamine oxidase activity and more importantly, the adverse effect profile of tricyclic antidepressants[2]. Venlafaxine hydrochloride has no affinity for brain muscarinic, cholinergic, histaminergic or adrenergic receptors. Literature survey reveals various analytical methods reported for estimation of venlafaxine hydrochloride in API and pharmaceutical formulations includes UV spectrophotometric[3,4] and HPLC[5-8]. Out of these analytical methods HPLC[9-11] is most widely used technique in quantitative analysis of drugs because of its accuracy. The developed HPLC methods have a drawbacks of long retention time and complex mobile phase compositions. So there is a need of a RP-HPLC method for Venlafaxine hydrochloride in which mobile phase composition is simple and short retention time. So, with this objectives authors proposed a RP-HPLC method which is rapid and simple. The present study, a new RP-HPLC method was developed for estimation of venlafaxine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulation, which shown high reproducibility, sensitivity and economical. The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines [12-14].

Figure 1. Chemical structure of venlafaxine hydrochloride.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

All the solvents used in the study were of HPLC grade and supplied by Merck India, Mumbai. Venlafaxine hydrochloride (VEN) pure was obtained from R.A Chem, Hyderabad. A capsule formulation (VENLOR-XR, Cipla) claim to contain 75 mg of venlafaxine hydrochloride in each capsule is purchased from local pharmacy.

Instrumentation

Chromatographic separation was performed on a Cyberlab HPLC system equipped with a Flowrosil C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, with 5 μm particle), single pumps, variable wave length detector and Rheodyne injector with 20 μl loop volume. 'LC -100' software was used to collect and process the data. Ultra sonicator (Citizen ultra sonicator) was used for sonicating the drug and sample solution. Digital weighing balance (SHIMADZU AUX 220) used for weighing.

Chromatographic conditions

The chromatographic system used for method development and validation includes the LC-P100 pump, variable wavelength programmable LC-UV100 UV detector and SCL20A system controller at CYBERLAB HPLC. A Rheodyne injector 7725i equipped with a 20 μL loop was used and the data was recorded and evaluated using LC solution software version 5.0. Separation was performed at Flowrosil C18 (250 × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm) at the ambient temperature. A mixture of 0.1 % ortho-phosphoric acid in water and methanol in a 10: 90 v / v ratio was found to be the ideal mobile phase for the ideal chromatographic analysis of venlafaxine hydrochloride. The solvent mixture was filtered through a 0.22 μ membrane filter and sonicated before use. It is pumped through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 mL / min. The injection volume is maintained in the column at 20 μL and room temperature. The column was balanced by pumping the mobile phase through the column for at least 20 min before injecting the drug solution. The detection was monitored at 225 nm. Run time is set to 10 minutes. Optimized chromatographic conditions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Optimized chromatographic conditions.

Parameters	Conditions
Stationary Phase (Column)	Flowrosil C18 (250x 4.6mm, 5μm).
Mobile Phase	Methanol: 0.1% ortho-phosphoric acid (90:10,v/v)
Flow rate(ml/min)	1.0 mL/min
Run time(min)	5 min
Column temperature (°C)	Ambient
Volume of injection loop(μL)	20
Detection wavelength(nm)	225 nm
Retention time(min)	2.41

Fig. 2: Chromatogram of standard solution of venlafaxine hydrochloride.

Preparation of mobile phase

The mobile phase methanol and 0.1% v/v ortho phosphoric acid were taken in ratio of 90:10 v/v and were filtered separately through membrane filter (Nylon disc filter of 0.22 μ) using vacuum filter and sonicated for 1 hour in ultrasonic bath before use. These sonicated mobile phases were run through the column.

Preparation of standard stock solutions

Accurately weigh individually 10 mg of Venlafaxine hydrochloride and transferred separately to 10 ml of volumetric flasks. And make up to 10 ml with acetonitrile and sonicate it for 10 min (1000 μ g/ml). Then the above solution was diluted with mobile phase to prepare 100 μ g/ml.

Preparation of sample solution

Taken 10 capsules of Venlafaxine hydrochloride and weighed and they were transferred into mortar and triturated to make a fine powder. From this take weight equivalent to 10 mg of VEN in 10 ml volumetric flasks. And make up the volume up to 10 ml with the acetonitrile. It will give 1000 μ g/ml (stock solution). The above solution was filtered through 0.22 μ m nylon membrane filter and further dilutions were done with mobile phase for analysis.

Method Validation

The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines by evaluating linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, detection limit, quantification limit and stability. Coefficients of variation and relative errors of less than 2 % were considered acceptable.

System Suitability Test

Before performing validation experiments, system suitability test (SST) has to be applied to indicate that HPLC system and method are capable of providing data with admissible quality. SST was performed by investigating capacity factor, tailing factor, theoretical plates number, and also relative standard deviation (RSD) of the peak areas.

Stability

Stability was assessed by analyzing QC standard solutions after keeping them at room temperature for 48 h. Obtained results were investigated as recovery values and compared to the freshly prepared solutions.

Linearity

A stock solution of venlafaxine hydrochloride of 1000 μ g/mL was prepared with mobile phase. From it, various working standard solutions were prepared in the range of 5 to 100 μ g/ml and injected into HPLC. It was shown that the selected drug had linearity in the range of 7.5-37.5 μ g/mL. The calibration plot (peak area of venlafaxine hydrochloride versus venlafaxine hydrochloride concentration) was generated by replicate analysis (n=6) at all concentration levels and the linear relationship was evaluated using the least square method within Microsoft Excel® program.

Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was carried out using one set of different standard addition methods at different concentration levels, 50 %, 100 % and 150 %, and then comparing the difference between the spiked value (theoretical value) and actual found value.

Precision

The precision of the method was ascertained from the peak area obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of the drug (22.5 µg/mL). The precision of the assay was also determined in terms of intra- and inter-day variation in the peak areas of a set of drug solutions on three different days. The intra- and inter-day variation in the peak area of the drug solution was calculated in terms of relative standard deviation (RSD).

Robustness

Robustness of the proposed method for venlafaxine hydrochloride was carried out by the slight variation in flow rate, analytical wavelength and mobile phase ratio. The percentage recovery and RSD were noted for venlafaxine hydrochloride.

Ruggedness

The test solutions were prepared as per test method and injected under variable conditions. Ruggedness of the method was studied by different analysts.

Detection limit and quantification limit

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were established based on the calibration curve parameters, according to the following formulas:

$$\text{LOD} = 0.32 \text{ SD/slope}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 1.01 \text{ SD/slope}$$

or detection limit = $0.32 \sigma/s$, quantification limit = $1.01 \sigma/s$, where σ is the standard deviation of y-intercept of regression line, and s is the slope of the calibration curve.

Specificity

The specificity of the proposed method was determined against blank and placebo applications. Here mobile phase was used as blank and excipients like starch, lactose, magnesium stearate were used as placebo.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method validation:

System Suitability Test

After setting the optimum conditions, system suitability parameters for the developed method were determined and compared with recommended limits. To determine the parameters, the study was performed with standard solution of 22.5 µg/ml concentration and the results were acquired from six injections. System suitability parameters of the method were demonstrated in Table 2. According to the results, all of the system suitability parameters were within the recommended limits and the method was found to be suitable for the analysis.

Table 2: Results of system suitability test (n = 6).

Parameter	Criteria	Result
Capacity factor(<i>k</i>)	$k > 2$	2.41
Tailing factor (<i>T</i>)	$T < 2$	1.40
Theoretical plates (<i>N</i>)	$N > 2000$	4880
% RSD (peak area)	$\% \text{ RSD} \leq 1$	0.74

Stability

The sample solution stability was analyzed by injecting the same solution at 0, 12, 24, and 48 h. Identical change was not observed in the developed method. Also, results were found within acceptable limits ($\% \text{ RSD} < 2$), which are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Stability data of venlafaxine hydrochloride (standard solutions).

Time (hr)	Assay(%)	% Difference
Initial	100.08	----
After 12 hr	100.02	0.05
After 24 hr	99.87	0.21
After 36 hr	99.16	0.92
After 48 hr	98.32	1.76

Linearity and sensitivity

Linearity study was performed with calibration standards with 7.5, 15, 22.5, 30, 37.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentrations. The standards were injected in triplicate. Calibration curves were obtained by plotting the peak areas against the given concentrations. The calibration curve was evaluated by the determination coefficient. The determination coefficient (R^2) of the calibration curves was 0.9981. Therefore, the calibration curve for venlafaxine hydrochloride was found to be linear within the range of 7.5-37.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentrations as shown in Fig.3. The regression equations were calculated from the calibration graphs. The sensitivity of the analytical method was evaluated by determining the limits of detection (LOD) and quantitation (LOQ). The values of LOD and LOQ are given in Table 4. The low values of LOD and LOQ indicates the sensitivity of method.

Table 4: Spectral and statistical data for determination of venlafaxine hydrochloride by proposed RP-HPLC method.

Parameter	Result
Detection wavelength (nm)	225
Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.5-37.5
Coefficient of determination (r^2)	0.9981
Regression equation (Y^a)	$Y = 13209x + 10786$
Slope (m)	13209
Intercept (c)	10786
Limit of detection, LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.32
Limit of quantitation, LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.01

^a $Y = mx + c$, where x is the concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$).

Calibration curve of Venlafaxine hydrochloride.

Accuracy

To study the reliability, the suitability, and the accuracy of the method, recovery experiments were carried out. Known quantities of the pure drug were added to the preanalyzed sample to make samples at the levels of 50 %, 100 %, and 150 %, and were assayed by the proposed method. Accuracy was calculated as the percentage of recovery. The recovery and relative standard deviation for each of the analytes are given Table 5. From the recovery studies it is evidence that the method is highly accurate and can give excellent results.

Table 5: Accuracy results.

% Level	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		Recovery (%)	Statistical Results		
	Formulation	Pure drug		Mean	SD	%RSD
50	22.5	11.25	99.34			
50	22.5	11.25	99.92	99.74	0.35	0.36
50	22.5	11.25	99.97			
100	22.5	22.5	99.87			
100	22.5	22.5	99.71	99.89	0.19	0.20
100	22.5	22.5	100.09			
150	22.5	33.75	98.64			
150	22.5	33.75	99.52	99.28	0.56	0.57
150	22.5	33.75	99.69			

Precision

The precision was demonstrated at three levels: repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility (between laboratories' precision). Each level of precision was investigated by 3 sequential replicate of injections of three concentrations of 22.5 µg/mL. The precision was expressed as relative standard deviation (RSD) or coefficient of variation (CV). The results of three levels of precision are shown in Table 6. The developed method was found to be precise as the RSD values for repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility studies were < 2 %, respectively as recommended by ICH guidelines (ICH Q2 (R1), 2005).

Table 6: Precision results.

Precision	Results		
	Concentration(µg/mL)	% RSD of Peak area	% RSD of Retention Time
Repeatability	15	0.89	0.02
	22.5	1.21	0.08
	30	1.11	0.12
Intermediate precision	15	1.42	0.08
	22.5	0.75	0.06
	30	0.67	0.06
Reproducibility	15	1.64	0.11
	22.5	0.78	0.17
	30	0.85	0.09

Robustness and ruggedness

Robustness of the method was studied by deliberate variations of the analytical parameters such as flow rate (1.0±0.1 mL/min), mobile phase composition (± 5 % organic phase) and analytical wavelength (±2 nm). The results are given in Tables 7-9. The result shown that have the negligible effect on retention time, recoveries and peak area of venlafaxine hydrochloride indicating the developed method is robust. Ruggedness of the method was carried out by different analysts. The results are displayed in Table 10. There is no variation in peak areas and retention time of venlafaxine hydrochloride from studies carried out by two analysts as indicated by % RSD < 2 gives the method rugged.

Table 7. : Change in Flow rate.

S.NO	VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE		
	Change in flow rate		
	0.9ml	1ml	1.1ml
1	403791	412300	420524
2	406089	414097	422176
3	409087	416023	424068
4	411812	417606	425901
5	414797	419230	427698
6	417912	420789	429080
Mean	410581.3	416674.2	424907.8
SD	5320.672	3179.044	3273.06
%RSD	1.29	0.76	0.77

Table 8: Change in Mobile phase.

S.NO	VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE		
	Change in mobile phase		
	85:15%	90:10%	95:05%
1	401065	411023	421083
2	405143	413421	423123
3	408233	415822	425209
4	411573	418322	427510
5	415222	420432	430102
6	419332	423112	432332
Mean	410094.7	417022	426559.8
SD	6683.158	4490.02	4252.057
%RSD	1.62	1.07	0.99

Table 9: Change in wavelength.

S.NO	VENLAFAXINE HYDROCHLORIDE		
	Change in wavelength		
	223 nm	225nm	227nm
1	410213	410023	411997
2	412910	412022	413766
3	415123	414286	415232
4	417211	416232	417211
5	419911	418433	418912
6	422196	420593	410322
Mean	416260.7	415264.8	406240
SD	4439.635	3957.599	4158.637
%RSD	1.40	0.95	0.62

Table 10: Ruggedness results of venlafaxine hydrochloride.

S.No	Drug	
	Change of analyst	
	Analyst 1	Analyst 2
1	404761	403632
2	406831	406212
3	408892	409056
4	411732	411731
5	413814	414237
6	416231	416347
Mean	410376.8	410202.5
SD	4341.362	4832.772
%RSD	1.05	1.17

Mobile phase stability

The stability of the mobile phase was evaluated, so the mobile phase was stored at 4–8 °C for 1 week. The aged mobile phase was compared using a freshly prepared one. The mobile phase was stable up to 1 week at 4–8 °C.

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to unequivocally assess the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present. Typically, these might include impurities, degradants or matrix. Specificity of an analytical method is its ability to accurately and specifically measure the analyte of interest without interference from blank or placebo. The peak purity of venlafaxine hydrochloride was assessed by comparing the retention times of standard venlafaxine hydrochloride and the sample, and good correlation was obtained between the retention time of the standard and sample. Placebo and blank were injected and there were no peaks. There is no interference of blank and placebo on drug peaks hence, the method is specific.

Sample Analysis

The developed and validated method was applied for analysis of capsule formulation contain venlafaxine hydrochloride. The sample was analyzed. Analysis results were evaluated using a calibration curve. The amount of venlafaxine hydrochloride in the samples was calculated from calibration curve equation and recovery and RSD values were determined. The results of analysis are given in Table 11. The recoveries were in good agreement with the label claims. The chromatogram obtained were clear as shown in Fig. 6. It was concluded that the method can be applied successfully for the analysis of venlafaxine hydrochloride in capsule dosage form.

Fig. 6 : Chromatogram of sample solution of venlafaxine hydrochloride.

Table 11 : Assay results from commercial formulation.

Sample	Labelled amount(mg)	Amount obtained* (mg)	Percentage Recovery* \pm SD
VENLOR-XR(Capsules)	75	74.87 mg	99.83 \pm 0.92

* Average of five determinations.

CONCLUSION

The proposed method for the estimation of venlafaxine hydrochloride was validated as per the ICH guidelines and it is simple, specific and reliable. Furthermore, this simple and rapid RP-HPLC method can also be used successfully for the determination of venlafaxine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulations without any interference from the excipient. Recommend future research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thankful to the management of Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences , for providing the instrumental and chemical facilities.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

ABBREVIATIONS

RP-HPLC - Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography
 HPLC - High Performance Liquid Chromatography
 API - Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
 VEN - Venlafaxine hydrochloride
 ICH - International Conference on Harmonization
 QC - Quality Control
 RSD - Relative Standard Deviation
 LOD - Limits of Detection
 LOQ - Limits of Quantitation

REFERENCES

- Entringer S: Venlafaxine. Drugs, 2019.
- Majed K.,Mechanism of sodium channel block by venlafaxine in guinea pig ventricular myocytes. Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics. (1999); 299(1): 280-284.
- Nikhil A , Prashant P. Analytical method development and validation of venlafaxine hydrochloride in solid dosage forms using UV spectrophotometer. Journal of Pharma Research . 2009;2: 1246-1249.
- Hosseini M. Application of UV-spectrophotometry and HPLC for determination of venlafaxine and its four related substances in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Turk J Pharm Sci .2011; 8(2): 91-04.
- Kaur J, Srinivasan KK, Joseph A, Gupta A, Singh Y, Srinivas KS , Jain G. Development and validation of stability indicating method for the quantitative determination of venlafaxine hydrochloride in extended release formulation using high performance liquid chromatography. J Pharm Bioall Sci .2010; 2: 22-6.
- Larissa SB, Paulo O, Fabio M, Borgmann HM, Silvia, Marcela ZA , Simone GC. Development and validation of a stability-indicating LC method for the determination of venlafaxine in extended-release capsules and dissolution kinetic studies. Journal of Chromatographic Science 2009; 47(9): 770-6.

7. Vanita S, Dannana G, Shivakumar N Development and validation of a rapid RP-HPLC method for the determination of venlafaxine hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms using experimental design. E-Journal of Chemistry. 2009; 6(4): 1091-02.
8. Ajitha A ,Rani GS. Stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation for determination of related substance in venlafaxine hydrochloride tablets. Int J Pharm Sci & Res. 2020; 11(8): 3923-29.
9. Kumar HT, Sri SD, Rao KVP and Rao YS. Validated RP- HPLC Method For Determination Of Rosuvastatin Calcium In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Formulation. Int J Pharm Sci & Res. 2015; 6(7): 1000-05.
10. Kumar TH, Jhanavi D, Rao KVP and Rao YS. RP-HPLC method for quantification of orotic acid in capsule formulation. Int J Pharm Sci & Res. 2019; 10(5): 2343-7.
11. Kumar HT, Prajna CKK, Rao KVP, Rao YS. RP-HPLC Method For Estimation Of Tramadol Hydrochloride And Paracetamol In Pharmaceutical Formulation. GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences .2019; 8(1):89-97.
12. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guidelines, Validation of analytical procedure: Text and methodology'Q2(R1);2005.
13. ICH. Q2B Validation of analytical procedure: Methodology. International conference on harmonization, Geneva;1996.
14. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guideline, Validation of analytical procedure: Methodology (Q2B); 1996.

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